

DEVELOPING READING LITERACY IN RUSSIAN LANGUAGE AND LITERATURE LESSONS

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Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются методы и приёмы формирования читательской грамотности учащихся на уроках русского языка и литературы. Анализируются современные педагогические технологии, направленные на развитие умения понимать, интерпретировать и критически оценивать текст.

Ключевые слова: читательская грамотность, анализ текста, русский язык, педагогические технологии, интерпретация текста, критическое мышление.

Abstract: The article discusses methods and techniques for developing students' reading literacy in Russian language and literature lessons. Modern pedagogical technologies aimed at developing the ability to understand, interpret and critically evaluate text are analyzed.

Key words: reading literacy, text analysis, Russian language, pedagogical technologies, text interpretation, critical thinking.

Developing students' reading literacy is one of the most controversial tasks of modern education. This issue is especially relevant in Russian language and literature lessons, as these subjects provide opportunities to develop reading skills and the ability to comprehend texts of various genres and styles.

In the PISA study, reading literacy is defined as 'the ability of an individual to understand and use written texts, to reflect on them, and to engage in reading in order to achieve their goals, expand their knowledge and opportunities, and participate in social life' [1].

Reading literacy implies the ability of students to find, understand, interpret, evaluate, and use information presented in written form. The ability to work with a text, analyze information, identify the main ideas, and formulate one's own opinion are important skills developed in Russian language lessons.

Reading literacy encompasses a much broader range of competencies – from basic decoding, vocabulary knowledge, grammar, and text structure to knowledge about the world. Reading literacy also includes metacognitive competencies: the ability to recognize one's own misunderstanding, to restore and maintain comprehension at an appropriate level. The desired level of comprehension depends on the task the reader

sets for themselves. Historically, the term 'literacy' refers to mastery of a tool (a cultural means) that enables one to receive and convey information in written form.

In Russian language classes in secondary school, it is essential to carry out work aimed at developing reading literacy. First and foremost, this should take place during speech development lessons, where students become acquainted with texts, analyze the language of literary works, learn to identify the main idea and the structural parts of a literary piece, get to know the characteristics of the characters, express their own evaluation of the events, and more. All of this can be encompassed within the main areas of work for developing reading literacy: integration and interpretation, comprehension, and evaluation of information.

The key here is awareness (when students choose a literary work for their assignment). It is precisely this awareness that should be taught during speech development lessons while working with a text. T. D. Polozova believes that 'reading fiction is a creative activity' [3].

The teacher plays a crucial role in the development of students' reading literacy. They must create a favorable educational environment that promotes the development of text-handling skills. This includes selecting a variety of texts that align with students' interests and skill levels, as well as developing tasks of varying complexity that cultivate different skills and focus on the development of various aspects of reading literacy. The reader should have two sets of skills developed:

1. Skills in working with text.
2. Awareness of what has been read.

To effectively develop reading literacy in Russian language lessons, it is recommended to use a variety of methods and techniques.

1. Comprehensive text work: Includes analysis of the content, structure, and linguistic features of the text. Students learn to identify key ideas, establish cause-and-effect relationships, and draw conclusions.

2. Linguistic analysis of the text: Involves a detailed study of the language tools used by the author. This helps students better understand the author's intent and gain deeper insight into the meaning of the work.

3. Text editing: Students are provided with a text that contains intentional errors or omissions and must correct or complete it. This develops attention to detail and the ability to critically evaluate information.

4. Essay-argumentation: Encourages students to express their own opinion on a topic, justify their point of view, and draw conclusions, which fosters the development of analytical thinking.

5. Technique "Reading with Pauses": The material for this technique is a narrative text. At the beginning of the lesson, students determine the topic of the text based on

its title. The text is read in parts, and after each pause, students predict the further development of the plot, which activates their imagination and ability to make predictions.

6. Technique "Working with a Questionnaire": This is used when introducing new material during the stage of independent work with the textbook. Students are provided with a series of questions about the text, to which they must find answers. The questions and answers are given not only in a direct form but also in an indirect form, requiring analysis and reasoning, and relying on personal experience.

7. Technique "Brainstorming": This technique helps activate younger students, assists in solving problems, and develops non-standard thinking. Such an approach does not confine the child to correct or incorrect answers. Students can express any opinion that helps find a solution to a difficult situation.

With the help of the suggested techniques and methods, students can be given the opportunity to view the reading process from a different perspective, not only engaging them in a pleasant "conversation" with the book but also in thoughtful reading.

The following methods are effectively used in developing reading literacy among senior school students:

The Method of Creative Reading

The goal and specificity of this method lie in activating artistic perception, in shaping through artistic means the emotional experiences, artistic inclinations, and abilities of students. Reading a literary text is qualitatively different from reading a scientific or journalistic text. This method is expressed in various teaching techniques. Let us name some of these techniques:

- Expressive reading by the teacher, reading by masters of the spoken word, individual scenes from plays performed by actors (on records, via computer, or on television);
- Teaching students expressive reading;
- Reading of literary text by the teacher with comments (commented reading) and a brief explanation aimed at facilitating correct and as deep as possible emotional perception of the work;
- A discussion that activates students' immediate impressions of the recently read work.

Heuristic Method

At this stage, the main material to be studied remains the literary work, but a more in-depth analysis inevitably links with the study of elements of literary science depending on the curriculum of the class, the age, and the development of the students.

Mastering a work, its analysis, is usually connected with resolving artistic,

moral, social, or philosophical problems posed by the writer. The teacher's task is to help students identify these problems, find ways to solve them in the literary text, teach them to analyze the work, teach them to reason, and express their thoughts in a coherent, sequential, and argumentative speech – whether oral or written. The heuristic method contributes to students' mastery of methods for analyzing literary works, concepts from literary theory, facts, and patterns in the historical-literary process. The heuristic (partially search-based) method is characterized by the following techniques:

- constructing a logically clear system of questions (for text analysis of a literary work, for historical-literary issues) that would lead students' thoughts from observation of the phenomenon to its analysis, from conclusions of a specific nature to more general conclusions;
- building a system of tasks based on the literary text or critical articles (tasks are completed orally or in writing);
- setting a problem by the teacher or suggested by students, conducting a debate. Impressions of the students from the recently read work.

Research Method

The goal of the research method is to reveal new aspects of the studied subject that have not been covered in previous lessons, to develop the ability to independently analyze a work, evaluate its ideological and artistic merits, and refine artistic taste.

With the research method, students who have already mastered working techniques solve more complex tasks on their own, which require the ability to apply existing knowledge to new material and express reasoned, evidence-based judgments. Techniques of the research method include:

- The teacher presents a problem to the entire class, with various aspects of this problem being developed either by student groups or individually;
- Preparation of reports and presentations as opponents;
- Independent analysis of a work not covered by the curriculum;
- Completion of creative assignments on aesthetic, literary, and moral issues.

Thus, the formation of reading literacy in Russian language lessons requires systematic and purposeful work. The use of various methods and techniques, as well as the active role of the teacher in this process, contributes to the development of skills necessary for successful learning and full participation in social life.

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